

**INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF ATTRACTING FOREIGN
INVESTMENTS IN ENSURING SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC
GROWTH OF THE COUNTRY**

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Annotation: The article highlights the significance of foreign investments, primarily foreign direct investments, in ensuring sustainable economic growth, deepening structural transformations, accelerating investment activities of enterprises, modernization, technical and technological re-equipment of production.

Key words: foreign investment, enterprises with foreign investment, export, tax regimes, taxes and customs duties, tax rates, tax credits and preferences.

Introduction. Today, ensuring political and macroeconomic stability, guaranteeing the protection of the rights of foreign investors and creating a wide system of benefits is one of the priorities of the rational investment policy in the country. In this regard, the head of our country, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, said: "World experience shows that any country that has pursued an active investment policy has achieved stable growth of its economy. That is why investment is the driver of the economy, in Uzbek terms, the heart of the economy, it is no exaggeration. Along with investment, new technologies, advanced experiences, and highly qualified specialists will enter various industries and sectors, regions, and entrepreneurship will develop rapidly" [1]. In the third important direction of the Strategy of Actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 - further development of international economic cooperation, including expanding relations with leading international and foreign financial institutions, continuing to implement a well-thought-out foreign debt policy, attracted foreign investment and special attention is

paid to ensure the issues of effective use of loans [2]. In order to ensure the implementation of the important issues defined in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev to the Oliy Majlis and the Strategy of Actions on December 28, 2018, the implementation of projects with a total value of 16.9 trillion soums and 8.1 billion US dollars "To be implemented in the year of active investments and social development" "State program" was adopted [3] The important priorities of this program in the field of economic development and active attraction of investments are to ensure macroeconomic stability, create the necessary conditions for healthy competition, fundamentally improve the business and investment environment, seriously reduce the state's participation in the economy, high economic it is important to maintain growth rates, fight against the "secret" economy and sharply reduce its share, and continue to liberalize the currency policy. In 2018, 18 interstate visits were made and investment agreements worth 50 billion US dollars were reached.

Today, 456 projects worth 23 billion US dollars are being implemented in our country at the expense of foreign investments. Currently, many foreign-invested enterprises are being established in our country and they are operating in various industries. The increase in the number of foreign-invested enterprises is primarily explained by the political stability in the country and the improvement of the legal basis of investment activities. As of February 1, 2019, the number of foreign-invested enterprises was 7,810, which increased by 2,202 or 39.3% compared to the same period last year.

The main part of these enterprises belongs to the Russian Federation, Turkey, China, Kazakhstan and South Korea. 4116 of the enterprises operating with participation of foreign investments are joint ventures, and 3694 are foreign enterprises. In terms of regions, the main part of enterprises operating with the participation of foreign investments was 4865 in Tashkent city (62% of total enterprises), 863 in Tashkent region and 408 in Samarkand region. The enterprises with the least foreign investment were 78 in Khorezm region, 90 in Kashkadarya, 120 in Navoi region and 124 in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

The main share of foreign direct investments attracted within the framework of the regional investment program of our country corresponds to the light industry (24 percent), services (15 percent), production of construction materials (13 percent) and petrochemical industry (10 percent) [4]. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2012 "On Additional Measures to Encourage the Attraction of Foreign Direct Investments", creation of the most favorable investment environment for foreign investors making direct investments in the development of high-tech industries, foreign investment in the republic's regions the promotion of attracting investments and modern technologies, the system of guarantees and benefits for foreign investors and enterprises with foreign investments was further strengthened [5].

Table 1

The number of enterprises with foreign investments established in our country

Enterprises with foreign investments	As of 2018	As of 2020	As of 2022
Total number of enterprises	5992	6625	7123
Number of operating enterprises	5411	6220	6765
Number of non-performing enterprises	547	1545	2896
Number of newly established enterprises	442	750	1569
The number of enterprises established within the regional investment program	219	621	751

Tax benefits established by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 11, 2005 "On additional measures to encourage the attraction of direct private foreign investments" starting from the II quarter of 2012:

- operating in economic sectors and fields;
- it was determined that it will be applied to enterprises with foreign investments located in all regions of the republic, with the exception of tashkent city and tashkent region.

According to the decree, starting from July 1, 2005, the enterprises of economic sectors that attract private foreign direct investments will be subject to the payment of profit tax, property tax, a single tax payment for micro-firms and small enterprises on the main activities, if the volume of direct private foreign investments is as follows. tax benefits are given:

- From 300 thousand US dollars to 3 million US dollars
- for 3 years;
- From more than 3 million US dollars to 10 million US dollars
- for 5 years;
- When it is more than 10 million US dollars
- for a period of 7 years [6].

In order to create favorable conditions for the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship, to further strengthen the legal mechanisms of private property protection and guarantees, to eliminate bureaucratic obstacles to the development of entrepreneurship, to consistently implement measures aimed at improving the investment environment and business conditions, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan The decree of June 19, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of protection of legal interests of business by the state and further development of entrepreneurship" became important [7].

According to this decree, the integration of business entities of our republic into the international business community, ensuring the release of products of local enterprises to foreign markets, active promotion of national brands abroad, attraction

of local and foreign investments, as well as modern technologies, including the establishment of small industries and domestic free economic zones and within the framework of the implementation of projects related to the organization of modern productions for the production of competitive products, which are in high demand in foreign markets, the task of providing all-round assistance to business entities, including foreign investors, was separately defined.

Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted in order to increase the effectiveness of attracting foreign direct investment to the infrastructural development of the city of Tashkent, to inform foreign investors about the opportunities and potential of the capital, to create favorable conditions for attracting foreign investment and the implementation of investment projects. The decision of the court on January 4, 2019 "On additional measures to attract foreign direct investment to the infrastructural development of the city of Tashkent" is significant [8]. In the decision, the main tasks of the heads of Tashkent city hokims, district hokims and state administration bodies in the field of attracting foreign direct investments and the establishment of Investor Support Centers at the Tashkent city district hokims from February 1, 2019 were determined.

To increase the investment potential of the Republic, to attract investments to the priority sectors and sectors of the economy, to ensure the interdependence of the investment process with the production of products intended for competitive export, as well as the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. based on the tasks defined in the State program on implementation, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2019 "On measures to improve the management system in the field of investment and foreign trade" was adopted. According to the decree, the Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on the basis of the Ministry of Foreign Trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the State Committee on Investments, and its main tasks and directions of activity were determined [9].

In conclusion, the following suggestions can be made in order to further improve the ways of stimulating the activities of enterprises with foreign investments operating in our country through taxes:

- to accelerate the implementation of the open door policy towards foreign investors who bring to Uzbekistan technologies that meet world requirements and are involved in the production of competitive products;

- development of a mechanism for stimulating foreign direct investments involved in the creation of infrastructure for the development of high-tech productions and high-value-added products, including in small industrial zones and technological parks, increasing their production volume and export;

- to increase the incentive effect of incentives to enterprises with foreign investments in free economic zones, first of all, to accelerate scientific and technical development in the country and to introduce it into production, to develop the production of consumer goods competitive in the world market.

List of used literature:

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